

Peer Reviewed Referred and
UGC Listed Journal
(Journal No. 40776)

ISSN 2277 - 5730

**AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY
QUARTERLY RESEARCH JOURNAL**

AJANTA

Volume-VII, Issue-IV
October - December - 2018
English Part - II

IMPACT FACTOR / INDEXING
2018 - 5.5
www.sjifactor.com

Ajanta Prakashan

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ज्ञान-विज्ञान विमुक्तये

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www.sjifactor.com

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Ajanta Prakashan
Aurangabad. (M.S.)

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5. Role of Education and Family in the Construction of Gender Identity among Secondary and Higher School Children

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Abstract

It has been observed from the various research findings that the education and family plays an important role in developing identities among the girls and boys, which is very much helpful in the functioning and assigning roles and duties to the girls and boys in the school, societies and culture. In Indian Society parents, teachers' and schools' aims, disciplinary strategies and beliefs has direct influence on the professionals of girls and boys. Thus parents and schools should enhance personality of boys and girls by constructing appropriate identities of boys and girls according to the psychology of them. Thus boys' personality is constructed by giving care, cooperation and thoughtful guidance. Similarly, girls need development of self-concepts, and confidence, which can be nurtured by the school, society and parents.

Keywords: Gender, Gender Identity, Equality, Inequality, Feminism and Patriarchies.

Introduction

Gender plays an important role in assigning duties and responsibilities to the men and women in our societies and cultures, this role is provided by the formal, non-formal and informal education system to these men and women. The concept of gender also includes the expectations held about the characteristics, aptitudes and likely behaviors of both women and men (femininity and masculinity), (Educational & Research and Training, 2006). It has been observed from the various research findings that the education and family plays an important role in developing identities among the women and men, which is very much helpful in the functioning and assigning roles and duties to the women and men in the societies and culture. Thus it necessary for the education system and family to provide identity to both women and men (femininity and masculinity).

In constructing and developing Gender Identity, the family and school of a child plays a pivotal role. This was observed in most of the research studies around the world. In their

explorative research carried out in public sector schools, (Dean, Joldoshalieva, & Hussainy, 2007), observed that the inter-relationship of the structure of schools, the official curriculum, teaching and learning practices and teacher beliefs result in a gendered division of labor, gendered bodily and disciplinary regulations, gendered control of space, bodies and behavior, and teaching to perceived gender differential characteristics which serve to develop gendered identities of both girls and boys.

Gender -Identity

In his book (Trivedi, 2016), describe, Gender identity as a person's private sense, and subjective experience, of their own gender. Thus it is in one's private sense of being a man or a woman, consisting primarily of the acceptance of membership into a category of people male or female. The concept of Gender identity is that a person has a conception of himself as male or female. This concept is intimately related to the concept of gender role, which is defined as the outward manifestations of personality that reflect the gender identity. (Trivedi, 2016). As cited in (Trivedi, 2016), the role of the gender can be understood as a set of social and behavioral norms that, within a specific culture, are widely considered to be socially appropriate for individuals of a particular sex. The perception of gender roles includes attitudes, actions, and personality traits associated with a particular gender within that culture. Gender identity, in nearly all instances, is self-identified, as a result of a combination of inherent and extrinsic or environmental factors; gender role, on the other hand, is manifested within society by observable factors such as behavior and appearance. In his book (Trivedi, 2016) gave example about the gender identity, if a person considers himself a male and is most comfortable referring to his personal gender in masculine terms, then his gender identity is male. However, gender role is male only if he demonstrates typically male characteristics in behavior dress, and/or mannerisms. Thus, gender role is often an outward expression of gender identity, but not necessarily so. In most individuals, gender identity and gender role are congruous (Trivedi, 2016). Gender identity has direct impact on the personality and the stress level this has been observed by the findings and interpretations by (Baig, 2017). The findings suggest that, the stress management level of the higher secondary science students (Junior College) is moderate. As per the results obtained it has been observed that the, females' students possess more stress management than male students of higher secondary science students (Junior College) of Aurangabad District.

What is Gender?

India is developing and progressive country, the education system is also progressive in the policy of mass education it also stresses on the gender education. The National Policy on Education, 1986 put specific emphasis on women's education. It states that: "Education will be used as an agent of basic change in the status of women. In order to neutralize accumulated distortions of the past, there will be a well-conceived edge in favor of women. The National Educational system will play a positive interventionist role in the empowerment of women". (Educational & Research and Training, 2006)

It is observed by the (Educational & Research and Training, 2006), that the Gender is a social construct which impacts attitudes, roles, responsibilities and behavior patterns of boys and girls, men and women in all societies.

Definitions

As cited in (Esplen & Jolly, 2006), the definition Gender by, World Health Organization, 2001, transforming health systems: gender and rights in reproductive health,) "Gender refers to the economic, social and cultural attributes and opportunities associated with being male or female at a particular point in time"

As cited in (Esplen & Jolly, 2006), the definition Gender by, World Health Organization: "The word gender is used to describe the characteristics, roles and responsibilities of women and men, boys and girls, which are socially constructed. Gender is related to how we are perceived and expected to think and act as women and men because of the way society is organized, not because of our biological differences".(Esplen & Jolly, 2006)

As cited in (Esplen & Jolly, 2006), the definition Gender is, "Gender is determined socially; it is the societal meaning assigned to male and female. Each society emphasizes particular roles that each sex should play, although there is wide latitude in acceptable behaviors for each gender".

As cited in (Esplen & Jolly, 2006), the definition Gender is, "Gender is the division of people into two categories, "men" and "women." Through interaction with caretakers, socialization in childhood, peer pressure in adolescence, and gendered work and family roles women and men are socially constructed to be different in behavior, attitudes, and emotions. The gendered social order is based on and maintains these differences". (Esplen & Jolly, 2006)

As cited in (Esplen & Jolly, 2006), the definition Gender is, "Gender relations refer to a complex system of personal and social relations of domination and power through which women and men are socially created and maintained and through which they gain access to power and material resources or are allocated status within society".

As cited in (Esplen & Jolly, 2006), the definition Gender given by, Health Canada: "Gender refers to the array of socially constructed roles and relationships, personality traits, attitudes, behaviors, values, relative power and influence that society ascribes to the two sexes on a differential basis. Gender is relational - gender roles and characteristics do not exist in isolation, but are defined in relation to one another and through the relationships between women and men, girls and boys"

Gender Concepts and Terminology

As cited in (UN, 1997), the concept of gender needs to be understood clearly as a cross-cutting socio-cultural variable. It is an overarching variable in the sense that gender can also be applied to all other cross-cutting variables such as race, class, age, ethnic group, etc. Gender systems are established in different socio-cultural contexts which determine what is expected, allowed and valued in a woman/man and girl/boy in these specific contexts. Gender roles are learned through socialization processes; they are not fixed but are changeable. Gender systems are institutionalized through education systems, political and economic systems, legislation, and culture and traditions (UN, 1997).

Role of Gender Identity

Role of Family and Education in the development of Gender identity

Family plays an important role in the development of Gender role and identity, in his book (Trivedi, 2016), defined gender role as a set of societal norms dictating the types of behaviors which are generally considered acceptable, appropriate, or desirable for people based on their actual or perceived sex or sexuality. Gender roles are usually centered on conceptions of femininity and masculinity, although there are exceptions and variations (Trivedi, 2016).

As observed in (Oláh et al., 2014), the de-standardization (and possible re-standardization) of the family life course in the world, the significant knowledge gap on new forms of family life, transitions between old and new family forms and within-family relations, and the lack of explanations for the new patterns pose considerable challenges to policy making. As pointed out by the Family Platform, much remains to be known of the multiple ways in which

women's increasing educational and economic attainment and men's declining economic position in many European countries shape family lives, the decision-making processes about work and family, parenthood, the use of time in families and the daily and biographical practices of 'doing family' in old and new family forms in different policy contexts (Oláh et al., 2014).

In their findings, (Oláh et al., 2014), Investigates the complex interplay between the new social roles of women and men and the diversity of family life in contemporary in terms of (a) family formation and dissolution as well as parenthood, that is, transitions over the family life course, and (b) the organization of family life (reconciliation of work and care). Increasing diversity of family forms is rooted in more diverse demographic behaviors, constitutive for the family life course, and in a gender divide of paid and unpaid work at the household level, both strongly related to changing gender roles. Further (Oláh et al., 2014), observe the, in-depth studies on these processes, and focus on the parent-to-child relationships within diverse family forms, evolving family patterns of work and care, and strategies adopted to deal with insecure work conditions.

In their research, (Dean et al., 2007), concluded that, All students, both girls and boys have high expectations from schools. However, teachers' beliefs and the teaching and disciplinary strategies they use limit who girls and boys can become as persons and professionals. Boys, like girls, require being thoughtful, caring and cooperative. Similarly, girls require good self-concepts, and confidence that comes from it. All these are important components of anyone's personality and schools should help both boys and girls to acquire the whole range of person traits. Further, in the all the schools, education was focused on preparing boys for their future roles as breadwinners and girls as homemakers rather than preparing them to choose from the range of professions based on their goals, personality and potential and not their gender alone. Further (Dean et al., 2007), observed that, some girls despite being considered weak and less intelligent continued to enjoy their studies and aspired to be in high status professions, challenging their traditional gender roles. In his book, (Trivedi, 2016), states that, Gender roles and construction of identities are defined by the socio-cultural norms of any society. In India most of the societies and the family systems are based on the gender roles and identities, this predesigned gender roles and Gender identities help members of the family to run the family with bound responsibilities. There is inequality by the parents in assigning roles to their children, for example, when dividing up household chores, boys may be asked to take out

the garbage or perform other tasks that require strength or toughness, while girls may be asked to fold laundry or perform duties that require neatness and care. It has been found that fathers are firmer in their expectations for gender conformity than are mothers, and their expectations are stronger for sons than they are for daughters. This is true in many types of activities, including preference of toys, play styles, discipline, chores, and personal achievements. As a result, boys tend to be particularly attuned to their father's disapproval when engaging in an activity that might be considered feminine, like dancing or singing. In their research study, (van der Vleuten, Jaspers, Maas, & van der Lippe, 2016), took longitudinal data which is collected from the adolescents at age 15 and 16, the sample collected is (N=1062), According to this study the adolescents internalize gender expectations as to what is "appropriate" male and female behavior in their gender ideology. Further in their study (van der Vleuten, Jaspers, Maas, & van der Lippe, 2016), observes, that the, gender ideology can affect educational choices by influencing, evaluation of adolescents of their competence in certain subjects, finding important things in a future occupation and the school subject they prefer for their study. Multinomial path models show that gender ideology shapes boys' occupational values and subject preferences, whereas for girls it shapes their competence beliefs. Only for boys this leads to gender-stereotypical educational choices, however. Our results support the idea that gender expectations are stricter for boys than for girls and may prevent men from entering more feminine career tracks.

Conclusion

In this study it can be concluded the education and family plays an important role in developing identities among the girls and boys, which is very much helpful in the functioning and assigning roles and duties to the girls and boys in the school, societies and culture (Dean et al., 2007). In Indian Society parents, teachers' and schools' aims, disciplinary strategies and beliefs has direct influence on the professionals of girls and boys. Thus parents and schools should enhance personality of boys and girls by constructing appropriate identities of boys and girls according to the psychology of them. Thus boys' personality is constructed by giving care, cooperation and thoughtful guidance. Similarly, girls need development of self-concepts, and confidence, which can be nurtured by the school, society and parents. Further (Dean et al., 2007), observed that, some girls despite being considered weak and less intelligent continued to enjoy their studies and aspired to be in high status professions, challenging their traditional gender roles.

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